

Education Quarterly Reviews

Kundaeng, S., & Dhammabhissamai, P. (2022). Teacher Participatory Practices to Enhance Students' Leadership Skills. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 5(3), 372-386.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.05.03.552

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Education Quarterly Reviews* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Education Quarterly Reviews* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of education, linguistics, literature, educational theory, research, and methodologies, curriculum, elementary and secondary education, higher education, foreign language education, teaching and learning, teacher education, education of special groups, and other fields of study related to education. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Education Quarterly Reviews* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of education.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Teacher Participatory Practices to Enhance Students' Leadership Skills

Sarawut Kundaeng¹, Phrakhru Dhammabhissamai²

^{1,2} Mahamakut Buddhist University, Isan Campus

Abstract

This study aimed at helping students to improve their leadership skills by utilizing the methodology of Participatory Action Research in which two cycles of research (one cycle per semester) were conducted during the Academic Year of 2021. The three anticipated developmental outcomes of change, learning, and knowledge were gained through the practices, which were administered in the particular setting of the Noensangawittaya School in Chaiyaphum Province. The target group for development consisted of 191 high school students, and 13 teachers served as the study's co-investigators. The findings revealed the changes that had been anticipated. In accordance with the comparative analysis of the three phases (before and after the first cycle of practices and after the second cycle), it was discovered that in order to improve the students' leadership skills, the co-researchers had continued to increase their activities since beginning the first phase. In a similar vein, there had been advancements in the leadership skills of the students. Together, the research team, the co-researchers, and the school discovered that any form of development, which prioritizes democratic or participatory principles, will produce better results. Additionally, a grounded theory known as the "Model for Developing Students' Leadership Skills: The Success of Lessons Learned through Participatory Action Research at Noensangawittaya School" was developed from the practices, which had been employed in this research.

Keywords: Leadership Skills, Participatory Action Research, Learning by Practice, Gaining Knowledge from Practices

1. Introduction

Half (2021) said, "Few are born leaders, but everyone can be made a leader." Likewise, Patulli stated (2018), "Everyone has the potential to be a leader when they use their ability to influence and take action." Whereas Kruse (2012) drew on famous quotes about the relationship of education and learning to the development of leadership skills, "Education is the mother of leadership."- Wendell Willkie and Leadership and learning are indispensable to each other." - John F. Kennedy.

Taubenfeld (2021), who is an assistant editor for Reader's Digest, stated, 'Good leaders encompass ten skills: integrity, the ability to delegate, communication, self-awareness, gratitude, learning agility, influence, empathy, courage, and respect.' At the same time, he assembled leadership quotes from notable leaders around the world, which were consistent with the statement 'Everyone can be made a leader.' For example, the following quotes demonstrate the truth of the previous quote: "The ability to learn is the most important quality a leader can have." —*Padmasree Warrior, CEO & founder of Fable*; "The most dangerous leadership myth is that leaders are born—that there is a genetic factor to leadership. That's nonsense; in fact, the opposite is true. Leaders are made rather

than born.” —*Warren Bennis, American scholar, organizational consultant, and author*; “Leadership is not a person or a position. It is a complex moral relationship between people based on trust, obligation, commitment, emotion, and a shared vision of the good.” —*Joanne Ciulla, author, and educator*; and “Leadership is not about men in suits. It is a way of life for those, who know who they are and are willing to be their best to create the life they want to live.” —*Kathleen Schafer, CEO of Human Being Store*.

Regarding the development of student leadership skills, India Today Web Desk (2019) pointed out that leadership is the art of motivating, influencing, and directing a group of people to work together and to achieve the goals of a team. In each phase of life and at every stage of growth, leadership skills are a wealth that is worth possessing. It is for this reason that it is necessary for “students” to experience leadership opportunities during their schooling. If pursued and practiced with diligence, leadership can become well-implanted within an individual so that it can advance his/her professional and personal growth. The most crucial characteristics of a student leader are being goal-oriented, being honest, being hardworking, having a willingness to serve others, being a good listener, being a good communicator, and being a good decision-maker, as well as encouraging others, having a positive mindset, and being responsible.

Leadership skills can be developed for students. Fulton (2019) asked, ‘How can you develop student leadership in schools?’ He made the observation and explained that ‘These types of students are generally what we would refer to as “natural-born leaders.” However, does this ability make them good leaders? Does being a natural leader mean that anyone, who isn’t as charismatic or persuasive, can’t be a leader? What other traits and skills are needed in order for a person to become a good and effective leader? Fortunately for the world, leadership is something that can be taught.’ At the same time, he suggested the following guidelines to develop students’ leadership skills: ‘Work hard, listen to the others, communicate their desires, make the final decisions, encourage others in their tasks, maintain a positive attitude; and take responsibility for the outcome of the project.’

In accordance with the concepts of “Everyone can be made a leader.”, “Education is the mother of leadership.”, “Leadership and learning are indispensable to each other.”, “It is necessary for “students” to experience leadership opportunities during their schooling.” and “Leadership skills can be developed for students,” the research team was inspired to carry out the project: “Teacher Participatory Practices to Enhance Students’ Leadership Skills” for students at Noensangawittaya School in Chaiyaphum by utilizing the methodology of Participatory Action Research (PAR). In this research, 13 teachers were the co-researchers, and 191 high school students composed the target group for development. The research was conducted in accordance with the characteristics of the research methodology in which the researchers and co-researchers collaborated in conducting the research equally from the processes of planning, acting, observing and reflecting in a manner that is a spiral drill circuit with continuous operations. These processes brought about successful changes and sustainable development due to the commitment to participation at all stages, which enabled the research team and co-researchers to learn from all the practices. Ultimately, this would enable the school to develop new knowledge, which could be used as a model for the further development of leadership skills in this school.

2. Research Objectives

This research aimed at strengthening the leadership skills of students at Noensangawittaya School in Chaiyaphum Province by utilizing Participatory Action Research (PAR) methodology. There were 13 teachers, who served as the co-investigators, and 191 high school students, who served as the target group for development. Three development outcomes were expected: (1) there would be changes in the expected and non-expected outcomes of the practices, (2) the learning from the practices would be obtained by the research team, co-researchers, and the school, and (3) the knowledge gained from the practices would be used as grounded theory in the specific context of Noensangawittaya School.

3. Literature Review

Participatory Action Research methodology, which was employed in this research, focuses on a review of the literature in order to obtain a wider variety of theoretical suggestions to present to the co-researchers and to

integrate in the suggestions from their experiences, which would, thus, yield vigorous development. It is consistent with the principle: “Theory and practice should be interwoven, and for this reason it is useful to think of the process as braiding a rope where the two aspects are continually connected together” (Flinders University, 2022). Therefore, in order to obtain a variety of theoretical suggestions, the research team, studied the theoretical perspectives on the 6 following issues: 1) the definitions of leadership skills from the concepts of NCTE Publications (2018), Psychology Today Staff (n.d.), Roffey Park Institute (n.d.), Science of People (n.d.), Skills You Need (n.d.), Smith (2010.), Ulrich (n.d.), and Ward (2020); 2) the importance of leadership skills from the viewpoints of Management Study Guide (n.d.), Henry (n.d.), Mittal (2020), Sharma (2018), Tasneem (n.d.), Anglia Ruskin University (n.d.), and Skills You Need (n.d.); 3) the characteristics of leadership skills from the perspectives of Eastwood (2019), Krakoff (n.d.), Mayhew (2018), Tobak (2017), and Waters (2021); 4) the developmental guidelines for leadership skills from Chastney (2020), Cherry (2019), Dawson (2019), Francisco (2018), Julka (2018), Prossack (2021), Reddy (n.d.), Yan (2019), and Zigarmi (2018); 5) the procedures for developing leadership skills from the concepts of Marone (2017), Davies (n.d.), Kangan Institute (2021), Petsinger (n.d.), and Ulrich (n.d.); and 6) the evaluation of leadership skills from the notions of Big Dog’s & Little Dog’s Performance Juxtaposition (2015), Nettles (2014), Stevens (2008), and White (n.d.).

According to the results of the study of the literature on the six mentioned issues, the researchers considered the viewpoint that the development of principles, concepts, techniques, methods, and activities are essential to broaden the co-researcher’s perspectives on a variety of developmental approaches that strengthen the “Teacher Participatory Practices to Enhance Students’ Leadership Skills.” Therefore, the researchers presented 39 developmental guidelines (principles / concepts / techniques / methods / activities), which were derived from the synthesis of information from the scholars mentioned above: 1) being a visionary, 2) being motivated, 3) serving, 4) having creativity, 5) building a team, 6) having a flexible leadership style, 7) generating leadership intelligence, 8) recognizing the importance of personal power, 9) taking a positive approach, 10) taking initiative, 11) inspiring and motivating others, 12) analyzing strengths and weaknesses, 13) listening, 14) dealing with conflict, 15) modeling great leadership for others, 16) understanding your strengths and using them, 17) setting concrete goals and executing them, 18) motivating others, 19) finding a higher purpose, 20) continuing to learning, 21) communicating, 22) always seeing the bigger picture, 23) letting your actions speak, 24) serving as a role model, 25) being passionate, 26) taking more initiative, 27) improving communication skills, 28) gaining knowledge about leadership styles, 29) thinking critically, 30) advocating for creativity, 31) listening effectively, 32) following the role model, 33) being well-disciplined, 34) possessing a clear vision, 35) having the talent to delegate tasks, 36) trying new ideas, 37) upgrading traditional leadership skills, 38) developing a common leadership practice across an organization, and 39) being an inspiration (being a good leader depends upon how things get done).

4. Research Methodology

4.1 The types of Action Research

Carr and Kemmis (1992) categorized action research into three levels. Firstly, there is Technical Action Research, wherein the researcher acts as an outside expert, who brings his own ideas, plans, or projects to the participants. Secondly, there is Practical Action Research, in which the co-researchers are more involved with the researchers. Unlike the first type, the researchers’ ideas, plans, or projects are not totally put into practice. In contrast, the researchers will function as consultants to motivate, raise issues, and to direct the co-researchers to think, act, observe, and reflect. Thirdly, there is Emancipatory Action Research (also known as Participatory Action Research), which has an important aspect in which the researchers participate in the research along with the co-researchers in a collaborative manner that gives each party equal status.

The methodology of Participatory Action Research (PAR) was chosen for this research. According to the results of an analytical and synthetic study by Sanrattana (2018), written by Arhar, Holly and Kasten (2001), Carr and Kemmis (1992), Coghlan and Brannick (2007), Creswell (2008), James, Milenkiewicz and Bucknam (2008), Kemmis and McTaggart (1992), McTaggart (1991), McTaggart (2010), and Mills (2007), it was found that the PAR methodology is a research paradigm that is in line with the concept of critical social science or pragmatism.

It is a type of research that partially uses scientific methods and a participatory action approach in a manner of collaboration between the researchers and the co-researchers. In order to affect the improvement of practical changes and better living conditions, both sides share equal status in the processes of Planning, Acting, Observing, and Reflecting (PAOR) in a continuous spiral cycle.

4.2 The Cycles, Steps, and Ethics of the Study

Participatory Action Research (PAR) methodology operates in accordance with the Planning, Acting, Observing, and Reflecting (PAOR) process in a continuous spiral cycle. However, for this research, due to a limitation on the duration of the course, the research team determined that there would be two cycles (one cycle per semester) in the Academic Year of 2021. The participants included 13 teachers, who acted as co-investigators, and 191 high school students, who composed the target group for development. The operations in each cycle and each step were conducted as follows:

Cycle1

Step 1: Preparation consisted of 3 activities.

- 1) The research method was explained to the research participants, so they could understand and decide whether to voluntarily participate in the research in accordance with the Code of Conduct: “(1) the investigator must first demonstrate the nature of the research process and the benefits to the participants, and (2) those who do not wish to participate, must be recognized and respected for individual rights.”
- 2) A collaborative approach was designed in accordance with the Code of Conduct: “(1) Engage research participants in the design of the research process and (2) joint consultation are taken and recommendations are agreed upon by all parties.”
- 3) The lessons learned were acquired in accordance with the principles of: “(1) analyze, critique, and assess one’s self and (2) learn from both successful and unsuccessful actions and be involved in the process of learning together in a systematic way.”

Step 2: Planning consisted of 4 activities.

- 1) Brainstorming sessions were held to determine the following: “Based on the knowledge and experience of the co-researchers (Tacit knowledge mentioned in knowledge management), what should be done and how to develop leadership skills in students?” This is consistent with the principle: “Realize the potential, expertise, and being a stakeholder of the research participants.”
- 2) The research team presented the theoretical development guidelines from the results of the literature study (Explicit knowledge mentioned in knowledge management) to the research participants. The goal was for the participants to gain knowledge and understanding in accordance with the principle: “Research participants can equally access to various information.”
- 3) The action plan was determined by conducting brainstorming sessions to integrate “Tacit knowledge in Explicit knowledge,” which was in accordance with the principle of “listening to opinions from all research participants.” As a result of the action plan, 44 developmental guidelines, which based on principles, concepts, techniques, methods, or activities, were decided upon as shown in the research summary (Table 1).
- 4) The lessons learned were acquired in accordance with the aforementioned principles.

Step 3: Acting consisted of 4 activities.

- 1) Two sets of evaluation forms were created as follows: 1) Set #1 was the participants' self-evaluation form, which focused on the level of implementation of the alternative suggestions, and 2) Set #2 was the students' self-evaluation form on leadership skills. Both forms were used in the three phases (before and after the practices of the First Cycle and after the practices of the Second Cycle) in accordance with the Code of Conduct: “Research direction and expected outcomes arise from joint decisions.”
- 2) Prior to the practices of Cycle 1, the current conditions were evaluated by using the participants' self-evaluation form, which focused on the level of implementation of the alternative suggestions, and the students' self-evaluation, which focused on leadership skills.

3) The action plan was implemented based on the following principles: “(1) in a specific context, (2) diversified skills, (3) change-oriented, (4) action-oriented, and (5) sustainable development.” and in accordance with the Code of Conduct: “All research participants have influence on work.”

4) The lessons learned were acquired in accordance with the aforementioned principles.

Step 4: Observing was composed of collecting data from activities and practices by using an observation form, conducting in-depth interviews and group discussions, and by using examining records or journals, maps, audiotapes & videotapes, artifacts, and field notes, etc. This was carried out in accordance with the principle of: “recording of all study participants’ activities and practices” and taking into account the Code of Conduct: “(1) Any observation or review of documents for any other purpose must be authorized, and (2) Do not infringe on the copyrights of writings or other people's views without negotiation before publication.”

Step 5: Reflection

Reflection consisted of the 3 following activities:

1) After the practices in Cycle 1, the conditions were assessed by using the following: a) the co-researcher's self-evaluation form, which focused on the level of implementation of the alternative suggestions, and b) the students' self-evaluation form on leadership skills.

2) To reflect upon performance, brainstorming sessions were held to examine all the results of the steps that took place in Cycle 1 in accordance with the principles of: “(1) listening to the opinions of all research participants; (2) analyzing, critiquing, and performing self-assessments; (3) learning from both successful and unsuccessful actions and creating joint learning processes in a systematic way;” as well as acting in accordance with the Code of Conduct: “The performance results will remain visible and open for feedback from others.”

3) To acquire the lessons learned in accordance with the aforementioned principles, the researchers used Kurt Lewin's Force-Field Analysis (Lunenburg & Ornstein, 2000) in the performance of the reflection activities to identify and better understand the following: 1) the driving force powers and how they had been used to make changes, 2) how many of the powers had produced the expected changes, 3) what the resistances to change had been and how they had happened, and 4) then from the resistances to change, what were some of the suggestions that could be utilized to increase the driving force powers and at the same time, could reduce or remove all the resistances to change so that in Step 6, the results could be used for planning. This may be an improvement on the existing driving force powers or may be the discovery of a new, more efficient drive to replace an existing one. Alternatively, it could be both adjusting the existing driving force powers and adding new driving force powers.

Cycle 2

Step 6: Planning consisted of the 2 following activities: 1) creating the action plan and 2) acquiring the lessons that had been learned.

Step :7 Acting consisted of 2 activities: 1) following the action plan and 2) acquiring the lessons that had been learned.

Step 8: Observing was composed of collecting the data from the activities by using the observation form, the in-depth interview form, or by using the group interview form, and by examining or recording as was conducted in Cycle 1.

Step 9: Reflecting consisted of 3 activities: 1) assessing the current condition after Cycle 2 by using the co-researcher's self-evaluation form to assess the level of implementation of the alternative suggestions and using the students' self-evaluation form on leadership skills, 2) brainstorming to reflect upon the performance at each step in Cycle 2, and 3) acquiring the lessons that had been learned.

Step 10: Summarizing the results of the joint research was carried out by holding a workshop with both the research team and the co-researchers to record the results of the observations, the lessons learned, the evaluation of the current conditions in three phases (before and after the practices of the First Cycle and after the practices of the Second Cycle), as well as by examining the results from reflection in Step 5 & 9. The research results were summarized in accordance with the following principles: “1) noting the specific contexts; 2) listening to the opinions of all participants; 3) analyzing, critiquing, and performing self-assessment; 4) learning from both successful and unsuccessful actions; and 5) creating a joint learning process in a systematic way” In addition, the

results were summarized in accordance with the Code of Conduct “Consultation is jointly taken and suggestions are agreed upon by all parties” and “The results will remain visible and open for feedback from others.”

4.3. *The research site and research participants*

Noensangawittaya School in Chaiyaphum was selected as the research area due to its convenience, the potential of the research team, and the possibility of obtaining cooperation from the co-researchers. Thirteen teachers volunteered to participate in the study, and 191 high school students composed the target group for the development.

4.4. *Research tools*

1) The tools for collecting the qualitative data from the activities at different stages: In accordance with their appropriateness and the situation, the researchers utilized them based on the concept of Mills (2007) as follows: 1) an observation form, 2) in-depth interviews and group discussions, and 3) an examining record or journal, maps, audiotapes & videotapes, artifacts, and field notes, etc.

2) The Co-researchers' self-evaluation form focusing on the level of implementation of the alternative suggestions: The research team and co-researchers jointly created the form to allow the co-researchers to self-evaluate their levels of implementation of the alternative suggestions in the three phases (before and after the practices of the First Cycle and after the practices of the Second Cycle). The form was categorized by a 5-rating scale: the most, very, neutral, a little, and the least. This evaluation form was neither proofed by a qualified person to check the Content Validity for the IOC: Indices of Item-Objective Congruence, nor was it tried-out with a sample to determine the Alpha Coefficient of Reliability because the questions in the form had been developed based upon the "Common Intention" of the research team and the co-researchers and had centered on the results of brainstorming to integrate “Tacit knowledge + Explicit knowledge” in the planning phase of Cycle 1.

3) Student's Self-Assessment Form on Leadership Skills: The researchers and co-researchers built upon the results of the study of traits or attributes that demonstrate leadership skills from the viewpoints of Eastwood (2019), Krakoff (n.d.), Mayhew (2018), Tobak (2017), and Waters (2021) and from the study of the concepts of assessing leadership skills from the perspectives of Maxwell (2007), Nettles (2014), Nohria and Khurana (2009), Northouse (2011), and White (2007). This assessment, which consisted of 25 questions, had a 5-rating scale: the most, very, neutral, a little, and the least.

This assessment form was examined for the Indices of Item-Objective Congruence: IOC in accordance with Rovinelli and Hambleton (1977), by five experts in the fields of Educational Administration and Educational Measurements & Assessments. It revealed that all the questions scores had exceeded the specified criteria of 0.50 for all items, which indicated that the questions in the assessment had been consistent with the developmental objectives from the perspective of Chaichanawiroe & Vantum (2017).

This assessment was tried out with 30 students at another school (not in the research area) to determine the Cronbach's alpha or coefficient alpha, which is a reliability coefficient that provides a method for measuring the internal consistency of tests. It was discovered that the overall reliability coefficient had been 0.89, which was higher than the specified criteria of 0.70 (UCLA: Statistical Consulting Group, 2016) and suggested that the items had shown a relatively high internal consistency.

4.5. *Data Collection and Analysis*

The researchers and co-researchers contributed to every step of data collection by using the above-mentioned tools in accordance with the principle: ‘All activities and practices of all co-researchers are recorded.’ The quantitative data from both self-assessments was analyzed by Mean ($\bar{x}$) and Standard Deviation (S.D.) descriptive statistics.

Regarding the qualitative data, it was the actual data that had been obtained from observations, interviews, and recordings. The data analysis process was as follows: 1) the integrity of the data was checked to determine whether or not it had met the desired objectives; 2) the reliability of the data information was checked in order to discover

whether or not it corresponded to the actual situation by comparing the results of each record and the recording results from using the different data collection tools; and 3) the data was presented in the form of a deep critical description (Thick, Critical Description) through storytelling and in accordance with the facts and neutrality (Factual and Neutral Manner). The data also contained descriptive evidence, such as numbers, statistics, tables, graphics, photographs, and direct quotes (verbatim). In addition, there were the informants' improvised conversations that had pointed to a wide variety of feelings and perceptions on the same issues, which may support or contradict each other.

5. Research results

In accordance with the research objectives, the research results were as follows: 1) there were both expected and unexpected changes, and the expected changes were gleaned from the results of the co-researchers' self-assessments based upon the degree of implementation of the alternative suggestions and the results of the students' self-assessment on leadership skills in the 3 phases (before and after the First Cycle and after the Second Cycle); 2) the learning that was derived from the practices conducted by the researcher, the co-researchers, and the school; and 3) the body of knowledge derived from the practices.

5.1. Expected Changes

1) The implementation of alternative suggestions by co-researchers was higher. According to the evaluation of the level of implementation of the developmental guidelines, which were the principles, concepts, techniques, methods or activities of the 13 participants in the 3 phases (before and after the practices of the First Cycle and after the practices of the Second Cycle), it was found that Mean values had increased respectively at 2.56, 2.74, and 2.87. This indicated that the co-researchers had used the alternative suggestions as developmental guidelines and had accordingly put them into action more often. Considering the Standard Deviations, it was found that there had been low values in all 3 phases, which were 0.56, 0.55, and 0.67, respectively. These values indicated a low variance in the opinions of the participants at each stage. The results of the analysis of the overall and discrete data are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: A comparison of the results of the co-researchers' self-assessment to the level of implementation of alternative suggestions by comparing 3 phases: Before and After the practices of the First Cycle and after the practices of the Second Cycle

Alternative Suggestions on the Developmental Approaches in Terms of Principles, Concepts, Techniques, Methods, and Activities that were expected to be Implemented by the Co-Researchers	Assessment Results: Before the Practices in Cycle 1		Assessment Results: After the Practices in Cycle 1		Assessment Results: After the Practices in Cycle 2	
	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	$\bar{x}$	S.D.
1. Students are enabled to present their work in class.	1.92	0.64	2.23	0.43	2.77	0.44
2. Students are enabled to work together.	2.76	0.43	2.92	1.03	3.15	0.69
3. Students are enabled to do volunteer activities.	2.46	0.77	2.69	0.63	2.77	0.60
4. Students are encouraged to try and to make mistakes.	2.69	0.48	3.07	0.27	3.15	0.55
5. Students are encouraged to express their visions.	2.30	0.48	2.53	0.51	2.69	0.75
6. Students are encouraged to develop their visions.	2.53	0.51	2.61	0.50	2.85	0.69
7. Students are encouraged to be motivated.	2.46	0.51	2.53	0.51	2.62	0.77
8. Students are encouraged to show leadership (Service).	2.84	0.55	3.07	0.49	3.15	0.80
9. Students are encouraged to show creativity.	2.46	0.51	2.61	0.50	2.85	0.80
10. Students are encouraged to build their teams.	3.07	0.49	3.23	0.92	3.31	0.48
11. Students are encouraged to upgrade traditional leadership skills.	3.00	0.57	3.15	0.80	3.23	0.60
12. Students are encouraged to develop a common leadership practice across the organization.	2.76	0.72	2.92	0.27	3.00	0.82

Alternative Suggestions on the Developmental Approaches in Terms of Principles, Concepts, Techniques, Methods, and Activities that were expected to be Implemented by the Co-Researchers	Assessment Results: Before the Practices in Cycle 1		Assessment Results: After the Practices in Cycle 1		Assessment Results: After the Practices in Cycle 2	
	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	$\bar{x}$	S.D.
13. Students are encouraged to have flexible leadership skills.	2.53	0.51	2.69	0.48	2.85	0.55
14. Students are encouraged to generate Leadership Intelligence.	2.76	0.72	2.92	1.03	3.00	0.71
15. Students are encouraged to perceive the importance of personal power.	2.92	0.49	3.07	0.75	3.15	0.38
16. Students are encouraged to develop approaches to positive thinking.	2.84	0.37	2.92	0.49	3.08	0.49
17. Students are encouraged to take initiative.	2.46	0.51	2.61	0.50	2.69	0.63
18. Students are encouraged to have inspirational and motivational skills.	2.07	0.75	2.23	0.43	2.31	0.63
19. Students are encouraged to be able to analyze their own strengths and weaknesses.	2.46	0.51	2.61	0.50	2.69	0.48
20. Students are encouraged to develop listening skills.	2.30	0.85	2.53	0.51	2.62	0.87
21. Students are encouraged to develop conflict management skills.	2.53	0.87	2.69	0.94	2.77	0.93
22. Teachers should serve as role models.	2.15	0.55	2.46	0.51	2.54	0.66
23. Teachers should be passionate.	2.23	0.59	2.38	0.50	2.46	0.52
24. Students are encouraged to be role models for leadership for others.	2.53	0.51	2.77	0.44	2.92	0.64
25. Students are encouraged to realize their strengths and be able to utilize them.	2.53	0.51	2.62	0.51	2.69	0.48
26. Students are encouraged to set concrete goals and to execute them.	2.46	0.66	2.61	0.50	2.69	0.63
27. Students are encouraged to motivate others.	2.15	0.68	2.38	0.50	2.46	0.88
28. Students are encouraged to seek a higher purpose.	2.00	0.40	2.15	0.37	2.23	0.60
29. Students are encouraged to be aware of being inspired to become a good leader depending on how to get things done.	2.23	0.43	2.38	0.50	2.46	0.66
30. Students are encouraged to learn continuously.	2.61	0.50	2.76	0.59	2.92	0.64
31. Students are encouraged to learn how to communicate.	2.38	0.65	2.61	0.50	2.77	0.83
32. Students are encouraged to incorporate bigger images of the future.	2.53	0.51	2.69	0.63	2.85	0.99
33. Students are encouraged to have the courage to speak up and to take action.	2.46	0.77	2.61	0.50	2.69	0.75
34. Teachers create and introduce activities that encourage students to take initiative.	2.61	0.50	2.76	0.72	2.92	0.49
35. Teachers conduct activities that improve communication skills.	2.92	0.75	3.07	0.64	3.23	0.83
36. Teachers conduct activities that promote knowledge about leadership styles.	2.92	0.27	3.07	0.64	3.38	0.51
37. Teachers conduct activities that develop the students' critical thinking skills.	2.84	0.55	2.92	0.49	3.08	0.76
38. Teachers conduct activities that advocate creativity.	3.23	0.43	3.38	0.65	3.46	0.88
39. Teachers conduct activities that promote effective listening procedures.	2.76	0.43	2.92	0.27	3.00	0.41
40. Teachers conduct activities that encourage students to become role models for others.	2.69	0.48	2.84	0.68	2.92	0.76
41. Teachers conduct activities that promote discipline.	2.76	0.72	3.07	0.75	3.31	0.75

Alternative Suggestions on the Developmental Approaches in Terms of Principles, Concepts, Techniques, Methods, and Activities that were expected to be Implemented by the Co-Researchers	Assessment Results: Before the Practices in Cycle 1		Assessment Results: After the Practices in Cycle 1		Assessment Results: After the Practices in Cycle 2	
	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	$\bar{x}$	S.D.
42. Teachers conduct activities that help students to develop a clear vision.	2.61	0.50	2.84	0.37	3.08	0.64
43. Teachers conduct activities that promote responsibility about assignments.	2.46	0.51	2.61	0.50	2.85	0.90
44. Teachers conduct challenging activities that encourage students to try new ideas.	2.60	0.75	2.84	0.37	2.92	0.86
Totals	2.56	0.56	2.74	0.55	2.87	0.67

2) Higher Leadership Skills for Students According to the results of the self-assessment of the leadership skills of 191 students, which was the goal for development in the 3 phases, it was found that the mean values rose as follows: in the pre-practice phase of Cycle 1 (2.47), in the post-practice phase of the Cycle 1 (2.58), and after the practices in Cycle 2 (2.75). It illustrated that this research had resulted in better changes in the leadership skills of students. In addition, the Standard Deviations had been at low levels of 0.62, 0.61, and 0.67 respectively. This indicated that there had been a low variance in the opinions of those students, who had been the evaluators. The results of the overall and discrete data analysis are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: A Comparison of the results of the students' self-assessment of leadership skills in the 3 phases: Before and After the First Cycle and after the Second Cycle

The Characteristics or Attributes that demonstrate the leadership skills expected from the students	Assessment Results: Before the Practices in Cycle 1		Assessment Results: After the Practices in Cycle 1		Assessment Results: After the Practices in Cycle 2	
	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	$\bar{x}$	S.D.
1. Students have broad ideas, attitudes, and visions.	2.27	0.52	2.37	0.56	2.46	0.66
2. Students like to seek out new learning.	2.67	0.76	2.77	0.73	2.92	0.64
3. Students give constructive criticism and solve problems.	2.60	0.56	2.70	0.53	2.85	0.55
4. Students always treat others with respect and dignity.	2.50	0.63	2.60	0.62	2.69	0.63
5. Students like to talk to people, and at the same time, they are good listeners.	2.50	0.63	2.53	0.57	2.62	0.51
6. Students are able to separate important points from non-essential points.	2.40	0.56	2.47	0.57	2.54	0.78
7. Students are honest and can be trusted by others.	2.47	0.68	2.57	0.68	2.77	0.60
8. Students are assertive when necessary.	2.30	0.60	2.40	0.62	2.69	0.75
9. Students admit their mistakes and correct them.	2.37	0.49	2.47	0.51	2.54	0.88
10. Students often set goals and are able to achieve them.	2.23	0.43	2.33	0.48	2.46	0.78
11. Students like to listen to others speak the truth.	2.30	0.53	2.43	0.57	2.54	0.52
12. Problem-solving is one of the strengths of students.	2.20	0.41	2.33	0.48	2.46	0.52
13. Students are comfortable in guiding and mentoring others.	2.47	0.68	2.60	0.67	2.77	0.44
14. Students enjoy using new methods and strategies.	2.47	0.68	2.57	0.68	2.62	0.77
15. Students try to solve conflicts with others.	2.50	0.68	2.63	0.61	2.85	0.80

The Characteristics or Attributes that demonstrate the leadership skills expected from the students	Assessment Results: Before the Practices in Cycle 1		Assessment Results: After the Practices in Cycle 1		Assessment Results: After the Practices in Cycle 2	
	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	$\bar{x}$	S.D.
16. When students encounter a problem, they immediately find a possible solution.	2.43	0.63	2.53	0.63	2.62	0.65
17. The students' actions reflect their core values.	2.47	0.57	2.63	0.56	2.92	0.49
18. Students like to listen to the opinions of others before making their own decisions.	2.43	0.50	2.50	0.51	2.69	0.85
19. Students open up and express their feelings to others.	2.40	0.62	2.57	0.57	2.92	0.76
20. Students listen closely to the thoughts of those, who disagree with them.	2.53	0.68	2.67	0.66	3.00	0.58
21. Students listen carefully to the opinions of others before making decisions.	2.67	0.71	2.73	0.69	3.15	0.38
22. Students make an emotional effort to convince others.	2.57	0.73	2.63	0.72	2.77	0.93
23. Students work hard to come to reach a consensus in situations where there is conflict.	2.67	0.80	2.83	0.75	2.92	0.86
24. Students are flexible about making changes.	2.77	0.73	2.87	0.68	3.08	0.76
25. Students enjoy communicating with others.	2.73	0.83	2.80	0.81	3.00	0.71
Totals	2.47	0.62	2.58	0.61	2.75	0.67

5.2. The unexpected changes

In accordance with the reflection activities in Cycle 1 and Cycle 2 and the workshop to jointly summarize the results of the research from the researchers and the co-researchers, it was found that the results of this research had brought about several unexpected changes in an improved manner. Firstly, in the beginning, the level of the co-researchers' participation in the activities had been low. However, after some time, they realized the importance of the activities and the effects that these activities could have on the development of their students, and in these activities, they began to demonstrate higher levels of contribution. Secondly, this action research focused upon gathering the teachers, who were the co-researchers, and on fostering unity and cooperation so that the goals that had been set together could be achieved. Moreover, it also created a good atmosphere in which to have positive interactions with each other and thereby, created a happy work environment in which they could work together without any pressure. Thirdly, the students showed greater degrees of assertiveness and leadership.

5.3. Learning from the practices

Based on what the researchers had learned, it was revealed that working collaboratively allows for the exchange of knowledge and enhances the success of the work in a better way than working individually. As discovered from the conversations and consultation meetings, the work became more systematic. In addition, dependent assistance contributed to collective benefits rather than to personal advantages. This strengthens relationships within the organization and team because everyone thinks together and works together to solve problems, which, in a concrete way, results in more efficient and effective performance.

Furthermore, the co-researchers learned that the work, which everyone had set as a common goal and which before acting, everyone had first come to have the same comprehension of, had created an understanding and a suitable common practice. This can be seen from the phenomenon of brainstorming for the convergence of the stream of experience and from the stream of academic expertise. This allowed the researchers and the co-researchers to bring together their knowledge and their work experiences to formulate a variety of alternative developmental

approaches. As a result, with the ideas that arose from their previous experiences, the co-researchers learned the value of integrating academic concepts. This differed from what they had previously done because in the past, they had often worked based on their same or similar experiences, which they had carried out without integrating any new ideas into the work or being creative.

Regarding the learning in the school, any development that places emphasis on participatory or democratic principles contributes to better development, such as in the case of developing leadership skills for students through various joint activities, which are based on experiential learning principles and on participatory learning. By using this method, the students were given opportunities to express themselves. Both thoughtful and practical skills, which can be applied to continually develop the students' potential, were shared with them.

5.4. Knowledge from the practices

Knowledge gained from the practices in this research represents a body of knowledge, which is based on the framework of Kurt Lewin's Force-Field Analysis (Lunenburg & Ornstein, 2000). The framework describes the relationship between expected changes and driving force power that is used to bring about change and how resistances to change can be overcome within specific contexts.

There were two expected changes: 1) it was expected that the co-researchers would implement the joint development guidelines and put them into action, and 2) it was also expected that the students would have developed leadership skills according to comparisons from the three phases (before and after the First Cycle and after the Second Cycle). The positive changes were identified based on the means and standard deviations.

The driving forces, which were employed in the research and which resulted in the two expected changes, consisted of the "three main driving forces": 1) the usage of Participatory Action Research methodology, in which the main element focuses on the equal collaboration between the researchers and the co-researchers in planning, acting, observing, and reflecting in a spiral cycle; 2) the usage of Buddhist teachings as a reminder to work with quality and success; and 3) an action plan, which had resulted from the integration of the co-researchers' previous experiences with the viewpoints from the academic literature study. The study was conducted under the principle of "Listening to all co-researchers' opinions" and in accordance with the Code of Conduct: "There was consultation, and recommendations were agreed by all parties." Moreover, there were the "three driving forces," which consisted of: 1) formulating the principles of collaboration between the researchers and the co-researchers that attaches importance to communication, (delegation, efficiency, ideas, and support); 2) setting the collaboration strategies that focused on positive attitudes, being accountable, reading a lot, continuing to learn, and using digital organization tools; and 3) identifying the steps to be used to implement the shared developmental approaches, which prioritized shared planning, shared implementation, shared observations, and shared reflection.

When examining the resistances to change and how to overcome them, the key findings consisted of the following: 1) most of the co-researchers did not have any knowledge of Participatory Action Research, which meant that the researcher had to provide them with a handbook that outlined the research step-by-step; 2) the co-researchers lacked the skills to integrate ideas from their own experiences with theoretical concepts, which, therefore, required the researcher to clarify the points, to encourage the co-researchers, and to use a case study as an example; 3) the co-researchers lacked the skills to take lessons learned and the skills to summarize learning outcomes from the practices, and this required the researchers to find good examples for them to study as a guideline for practice; and 4) the co-researchers had routine tasks to do, which led to time constraints for participating in the activities of many stages of the research. Furthermore, the researcher needed to periodically encourage and motivate them to take part in the research.

6. Discussion

This research is a study in the field of educational administration in which the research team has considered the response to the professional standards of educational institute administrators and education administrators, which

has been set by The Teachers Council of Thailand. Accordingly, the following theories and principles of educational administration must be utilized: 1) analyze, synthesize and create a body of knowledge from practices, 2) develop teachers and personnel in educational institutions so that they are able to perform their duties effectively, 3) create developmental activities for learners, 4) strive to develop colleagues so that they are able to work at their full potential, 5) develop work plans that are practical and effective by placing emphasis on obtaining permanent results, and 6) create opportunities for development in all situations (The Teachers Council of Thailand, n.d.).

Therefore, in addition to the six driving forces mentioned in this research titled, "Teacher Participatory Practices to Enhance Students' Leadership Skills", the research team also placed special emphasis on the principles of educational administration. Therefore, it is expected that those, who are interested in the results from this research, will use the following principles as reminders in their future studies: 1) Change management takes into account the principles of understanding changes, planning for changes, implementing changes, and communicating changes (Mind Tools Content Team, n.d.); 2) in management that is based on a democratic/participative leadership style, actions by them and for them are based on equality (STU Online, n.d.); 3) Administration uses an open approach, which places emphasis on the critical science of reflection for learning and creating new knowledge from practices in a specific context (Gordon, 2022); and 4) Theory Y management centers on the belief that the actual potential of the co-researchers can be integrated with the principles, concepts, or theories to result in effective practices (The Economic Times, 2022).

According to the practices of using the six driving forces and paying special attention to the four principles of Change Management, Democratic/Participative Leadership Style, Open Approach, and Theory Y, it was found that they had contributed to a body of knowledge that demonstrated the causal relationship of the forces for change in development that the researcher believes had resulted in both expected and unanticipated changes. Moreover, in the development, it was revealed what the resistances to change had been, and how the researchers and co-researchers had overcome the obstacles. Therefore, it is an important lesson that shows a successful operation, which can be used as a guideline to continuously develop the leadership skills of students in "Nernsangawittaya School" in the future. This research represents knowledge, which was derived from grounded theory and gained from the practices carried out in the specific context of this school. Therefore, it is not applicable to be referenced in general. However, some ideas or important events that have arisen from this research can be applied in other schools that are similar in nature or that are pursuing similar changes, in accordance with Coghlan and Brannick (2007) and James, Milenkiewicz, and Bucknam (2008).

7. Suggestions

Regarding the body of knowledge gained from this research, which the research team has called the "Prototype Model for Developing Student Leadership Skills: Lessons Learned from Participatory Action Research at Nernsangawittaya School", other schools, which desire to adapt or to apply the model in accordance with their own contexts, should visualize it as a system that demonstrates the interrelationship of expected changes, the driving forces that are used to produce the changes, the resistances to change, and the best ways to overcome the resistances to change in a specific context as shown in the illustration below:

Figure 1: The Prototype Model for Developing the Leadership Skills of the Students: Lessons Learned from Participatory Action Research at Noensangawittaya School

References

- Arhar, J.M., Holly, M.L., & Kasten, W.C. (2001). *Action research for teachers*. Merrill Prentice Hall.
- Big Dog's & Little Dog's Performance Juxtaposition. (2015, October 17). *Leadership self-assessment questionnaire*. <http://www.nwlink.com/~donclark/leader/survlead.html>
- Carr, W. & Kemmis, S. (1992). *Becoming critical: Education, knowledge, and action research* (3rd Ed.). Falmer Press.
- Chaichanawirote U. & Vantum, C. (2017). Evaluation of content validity for research instrument. *Journal of Nursing and Health Sciences*, 11(2), 105-111.
- Chastney, R. (2020, August 21). *How to develop and demonstrate leadership skills*. <https://www.futurelearn.com/info/blog/how-to-develop-and-demonstrate-leadership-skills>
- Cherry, K. (2019, updated 2022, May 23). *Ten tips for becoming a better leader*. <https://www.verywellmind.com/ways-to-become-a-better-leader-2795324>
- Coghlan, D. & Brannick, T. (2007). *Doing action research in your own organization* (2nd Ed.). Sage.
- Creswell, J.W. (2008). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*, (3rd Ed.). Merrill Prentice Hall.
- Davies, B. (n.d). *Five steps to develop your leadership skills*. <http://www.leadershipsolutions.co.za/5-steps-to-develop-your-leadership-skills.html>
- Dawson, J. (2019, April 8). *The path to leadership*. <https://www.amanet.org/articles/the-path-to-leadership/>
- Eastwood, B. (2019, January 24). *The 5 qualities all successful leaders have in common*. <https://www.northeastern.edu/graduate/blog/top-5-leadership-qualities/>
- Flinders University. (2022). *Link theory and practice*. <https://students.flinders.edu.au/content/dam/student/slc/academic-writing-skills/linking-theory-and-practice.pdf>

- Francisco, J. (2018, updated 2022). *Six simple ways to improve your leadership skills*. <https://aboutleaders.com/improve-leadership-skills/#gs.vdg5zd>
- Fulton, J. (2019, February 14). *How to teach leadership skills to your students*. <https://www.classcraft.com/blog/how-to-teach-leadership-skills-to-your-students/>
- Gordon, J. (2022, April 8). *Systems theory of management – Explained*. Retrieved from https://thebusinessprofessor.com/en_US/management-leadership-organizational-behavior/systems-theory-of-management
- Half, R. (2021, January 11). *The importance of good leadership skills*. <https://www.roberthalf.jp/en/blog/employers/importance-good-leadership-skills>
- Henry, M. (n.d.). *The most important leadership skills everyone should have*. <https://inside.6q.io/important-leadership-skills/>
- India Today Web Desk. (2019, October 20). *10 tips for students to learn the art of being an effective leader*. <https://www.indiatoday.in/education-today/featurephilia/story/10-tips-for-students-to-learn-the-art-of-being-an-effective-leader-1611256-2019-10-20>
- James, E.A., Milenkiewicz, M.T., & Bucknam, A. (2008). *Participatory action research for educational leadership: Using data-driven decision making to improve schools*. Sage.
- Julka, S. (2018, July 13). *Five ways to build and develop your leadership skills*. <https://elearningindustry.com/build-develop-your-leadership-skills-5-ways>
- Kangan Institute. (2021, December 15). *Ten steps to help you become a successful leader*. <https://www.kangan.edu.au/students/blog/become-a-successful-leader>
- Kemmis, S., & McTaggart, R. (1992). *The action research planner* (3rd Ed.). Deakin University.
- Krakoff, S. (n.d.). *The top 10 qualities of a great leader*. <https://online.champlain.edu/blog/top-qualities-of-a-great-leader>
- Kruse, K. (2012, October 16). *100 best quotes on leadership*. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/kevinkruse/2012/10/16/quotes-on-leadership/?sh=7b23bcd2feb8>
- Lunenburg, F. C. & Ornstein, A. C. (2000). *Educational administration: Concepts and practices* (3rd Ed.). Wadsworth Thomson Learning.
- Management Study Guide. (n.d.). *Importance of leadership*. https://www.managementstudyguide.com/importance_of_leadership.htm
- Marone, S. (2017, updated 2022, May 12). *Nine ways to develop your leadership skills*. <https://www.wrike.com/blog/9-ways-develop-leadership-skills/>
- Mayhew, R. (2018, April 13). *Describe strong leadership skills*. <https://yourbusiness.azcentral.com/describe-strong-leadership-skills-8434.html>
- McTaggart, R. (1991). Principles for participatory action research. *Adult Education Quarterly*. 41(3), 168–187.
- McTaggart, R. (2010). *Participatory action research or change and development*. James Cook University.
- Mills, G. E. (2007). *Action research: A guide for the teacher researcher* (3rd Ed.). Merrill Prentice Hall.
- Mind Tools Content Team. (n.d.). *The four principles of change management*. Retrieved from https://www.mindtools.com/pages/article/newPPM_87.htm
- Mittal, S. (2020, September 30). *Leadership skills: Why it's important to develop them in college*. <https://www.jagranjosh.com/articles/leadership-skills-why-its-important-to-develop-them-in-college-1521714835-1>
- NCTE Publications. (2018, June 29). *What does leadership in education mean to you?* <https://ncte.org/blog/2018/06/what-does-leadership-in-education-mean-to-you/>
- Nettles, D. (2014, August 17). *Leadership skills 360 inventory (general)*. <https://www.slideshare.net/DavidNettles1/leadership-skills-360-inventory-general>
- Patulli, J.J. (2018, May). *Everyone can be a leader*. <https://www.hsdinstitute.org/resources/everyone-can-be-a-leader.html#:~:text=Everyone%20can%20be%20a%20leader,around%20you%20to%20be%20successful>
- Petsinger, K. (n.d.). *Fourteen easy ways to develop leadership skills in your kids*. <https://www.lifehack.org/articles/communication/15-easy-ways-develop-leadership-skills-your-kids.html>
- Prossack, A. (2021, June 29). *Four ways to improve your leadership skills*. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/ashiraprossack1/2021/06/29/how-to-unlock-your-full-leadership-potential/?sh=3bd24a2844ac>
- Psychology Today Staff. (n.d.). *Leadership management*. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/basics/leadership>
- Reddy, K. (n.d.). *Eighteen best ways to improve leadership skills in the workplace*. <https://content.wisestep.com/improve-leadership-skills-workplace/>
- Roffey Park Institute. (n.d.). *Leadership: A guide to developing enlightened leadership -26 lessons from A to Z*. [https://www.ucd.ie/t4cms/Leadership%20Guide%20\(Roffey%20Park\).pdf](https://www.ucd.ie/t4cms/Leadership%20Guide%20(Roffey%20Park).pdf)
- Rovinelli, R.J., & Hambleton, R.K. (1977). On the use of content specialists in the assessment of criterion-referenced test item validity. *Dutch Journal of Educational Research*, 2, 49-60.
- Sanrattana, W. (2018). *Research in educational administration: Concepts, practices and case studies* (4th Ed.). Thiphawisut.

- Science of People. (n.d.). *What is leadership?* <https://www.scienceofpeople.com/leadership/>
- Sharma, V. K. (2018, May 7). *Importance of leadership skills for students.* <https://www.klientsolutech.com/importance-of-leadership-skills-for-students/>
- Skills You Need. (n.d.). *Leadership skills.* <https://www.skillsyouneed.com/leadership-skills.html>
- Smith, S.M. (2010, January 4) *What is leadership?* <https://stevenmsmith.com/what-is-leadership/>
- Stevens, L. (2008). *Leadership questionnaire adapted from "21 laws leadership evaluation"* in Maxwell, J. C. (1998 & 2007). *The 21 irrefutable laws of leadership: 10th anniversary edition.* Thomas Nelson Publisher. <http://csap.org/pdf/LeadershipQuestionnaire.pdf>
- STU Online. (n.d.). *What is democratic/participative leadership? How collaboration can boost morale.* Retrieved from <https://online.stu.edu/degrees/education/democratic-participative-leadership/>
- Tasneem. (n.d.). *Leadership – quality, significance & leadership qualities.* <https://www.yourarticlelibrary.com/leadership/leadership-quality-significance-leadership-qualities/46781>
- Taubenfeld, E. (2021, November 17). *114 inspiring leadership quotes to fuel your success.* <https://www.rd.com/article/leadership-quotes/>
- The Economic Times. (2022, July 17). *What is 'Theory X & Theory Y'.* Retrieved from <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/definition/theory-x-theory-y>
- The Teachers Council of Thailand. (n.d.). *Educational professional standards.* Retrieved from <https://maekongwa.thai.ac/client-upload/maekongwa/download/.pdf>
- Tobak, S. (2015, August 7). *Ten behaviors of real leaders.* <https://www.entrepreneur.com/article/249205>
- UCLA: Statistical Consulting Group. (2016, August 22). *What does Cronbach's alpha mean?* <https://stats.idre.ucla.edu/spss/faq/what-does-cronbachs-alpha-mean/>
- Ulrich, D. (n.d.). *What is leadership?* https://michiganross.umich.edu/sites/default/files/uploads/RTIA/pdfs/dulrich_wp_what_is_leadership.pdf
- Ward, S. (2020, September 17). *What is leadership?* <https://www.thebalancesmb.com/leadership-definition-2948275>
- Waters, S. (2021, November 2). *What makes a good leader? 18 leadership qualities explained.* <https://www.betterup.com/blog/leadership-characteristics>
- White, M.G. (n.d.). *Leadership self-assessment. (Free printable leadership skills test.)* <https://business.lovetoknow.com/free-business-templates-printable-forms/free-printable-leadership-skills-test>
- Yan, A. (2019 Updated 2022, February 14). *How to improve your leadership skills.* <https://www.investopedia.com/articles/pf/12/leadership-skills.asp>
- Zigarmi, D. (2018, August 10). *The evolution of leadership skills: Don't become extinct.* <https://www.chieflearningofficer.com/2018/08/10/the-evolution-of-leadership-skills/>